

Quantum Dynamic Probabilities $\exp(ipx)$ / $\exp(-ipx)$ And Lorentz Transformations

Francesco R. Ruggeri Hanwell, N.B. May 26, 2026

We have argued in previous notes that free particle quantum mechanics follows from $-Et+px = \text{constant}$, in that x, t and $x+\hbar/p, t+\hbar/E$ are solutions with the same value of the constant. We further argued that this is equivalent to a probability $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$ which has the same phase (and hence value) as seen in different frames.

In some notes, we argued that uncertainty in x follows from the uncertainty inherent in a rest particle with m_0 at $x=0, t$ transforming to x', t' such that $x'/t' = v$. Here we wish to consider this in more detail for the case of p and $-p$ because we have argued before that quantum mechanics introduces a dynamical probability, i.e. $\exp(ipx) \neq \exp(-ipx)$ even though the motions are mirror images for the same m_0 . We try to show that special relativity leads directly to this dynamic feature of the probability.

Quantum Free Particles

We have argued in previous notes that one may obtain free particle quantum mechanics from special relativity, in particular from the Lorentz invariant:

$$-Et' + px' = -m_0 c^2 t \quad ((1))$$

If x', t' are solutions (presumably following $x'=vt'$), then:

$$x'+\hbar/p \text{ and } t'+\hbar/E \quad ((2))$$

are also solutions. We argued that one may write a probability:

$$\exp(-iEt+ipx) \quad ((3))$$

The argument is a Lorentz invariant, meaning that one has the same phase as seen in different frames.

In some notes, we tried to argue that the reason that spatial uncertainty arises is that one transforms from $x=0$ to x' , and from t to t' when a particle is viewed from a moving frame. The above ideas, however, do not explain why free particle quantum mechanics is linked with a dynamic probability:

$$\exp(ipx) \neq \exp(-ipx) \quad ((4))$$

Lorentz Invariant And Transformation

In ((4)), we simply changed $p \rightarrow -p$. For the Lorentz invariant ((1)), however, one cannot simply change the sign of p without changing the sign of x because

$$-Et' + px' = -m_0 c^2 t \quad ((5))$$

Both p and $-p$ must yield expressions equal to the same $-m_0 c^2 t$ and so x' must change sign as well. One may see this change directly in the Lorentz transformation:

$$\begin{bmatrix} g(v) & g(v)v \\ v g(v) & g(v) \end{bmatrix} \quad ((6))$$

v and $-v$ yield different x' values.

In $\exp(ipx)$ and $\exp(-ipx)$, however, one considers a single frame in which one views two particles, one with p and one with $-p$. These two particles are equivalent to the same m_0 at rest at $x=0$, t viewed from two frames, one moving with v , and the other with $-v$. This leads to two shift values:

$$x' - 0 = -v g(v) \text{ for } -p \text{ and } x' - 0 = v g(v) \text{ for } p \quad ((7))$$

The same m_0 at $x=0$ in a rest frame transforms to two different x' values as seen from the two moving frames. There is not simply spatial uncertainty linked to $x \rightarrow x'$, but there is spatial uncertainty between x' for v and x' for $-v$ when one makes a Lorentz transformation. We suggest that this difference between x' for p , $-p$ must be retained for a probability expression in a given frame and we suggest that this is exactly what happens with

$$\exp(ipx) \neq \exp(-ipx) \quad ((8))$$

If one uses a momentum shift: $\Delta x = \hbar/p$ instead of $v g(v)$, then p should be linked with a positive Δx shift and $-p$, with a $-\Delta x$. For the probability there is no time and one has periodicity in space and so it is this shift which distinguishes between the probabilities p and $-p$. One may see that physically, the shift is linked with the complex part of $\exp(ipx)$, i.e.

$$i \sin(px) \text{ which is an odd function } \quad ((9))$$

One might ask: Why does one not simply use ((9)) as the probability? Two extra features must be considered. First, even though there is the shift $\Delta x = \hbar/p$, suggesting a resolution in space which is linked with 2-slit interference if slit separation is about \hbar/p , one should be able to interact with a 2-slit apparatus at any x . This suggests that $\exp(ipx)$ should be linked with a probability of interaction $P(x) = \text{constant}$. Secondly, p and $-p$ represent mirror motion (for the same m_0 , v) and so the probabilities $\exp(ipx)$ and $\exp(-ipx)$ are different (due to $\sin(px)$), but both have the same modulus.

We have suggested that quantum mechanics of a free particle is linked with center-of-mass classical motion $x=vt$ and quantum resolution. The quantum resolution picture, i.e. $\exp(ipx)$, however, cannot contradict $x=vt$. For instance, p and $-p$ and mirror motion, deals with motion and not interaction and so this equivalence feature is linked with the modulus of $\exp(ipx) =$

modulus of $\exp(-ipx)$, even though the two probabilities are not the same. They are not the same for resolution fluctuations which are directly linked to the manner in which p and $-p$ interact in a system which has spatial sensitivity, e.g. an incident beam and a reflected one in 1-D reflection-refraction at an n_1 - n_2 index of refraction junction. As a result, $\exp(ipx)$, by itself, is a combination of quantum resolution information and the more global (less informative) translational invariance in space idea.

Bound State Problem

A single particle bound state problem in a potential $V(x)$ is based on conservation of energy:

$$KE + V(x) = E \quad ((10))$$

Statistically, a particle is localized by the potential and so statistically one averages over $\exp(ipx)$ and $\exp(-ipx)$. The reason one uses $\exp(ipx)$ in the first place is due to its description of interaction. Given that

$$a(p)\exp(ipx) + a(-p)\exp(-ipx) = a(p) \cos(px) \text{ for } a(p)=a(-p) \quad ((11))$$

means that the \pm shift in x , which is important in one-direction statistical problems such as 1-D reflection-refraction at an n_1 - n_2 index of refraction junction, is not important in a bound state even though the absolute value of resolution \hbar/p still is.

Matter-Antimatter

We suggest that the above ideas may also be considered for matter-antimatter. An antimatter particle may collide with a matter particle to produce two photons. If the two particles have the same energy and one has 0 total momentum, then the two photons should be described by:

$$\exp(iEt) \exp(iEt) \quad ((12))$$

A particle has energy E and an antiparticle, $-E$ and so we argue that the time shifts for each must be of opposite sign so that one has

$$\exp(i[E] [t]) \text{ for each in order to obtain } ((12)).$$

Conclusion

In conclusion, for the Lorentz invariant $-Et' + px' = -m_0 c^2 t$, p is linked with x' and $-p$ with $-x'$. One may see this x' shift directly from the Lorentz transformation using v and $-v$. Even though one might argue that p and $-p$ are mirror motions (if m_0 is the same), they are linked with x' shifts from $x=0$ with different signs. We suggest that if one creates a probability which describes both p and $-p$ in some fixed x frame, then if the probability is a function of $-Et + ipx$, say

$\exp(-iEt+ipx)$, it has the same phase in any frame moving with constant v . One may, however, at the same time write $\exp(ipx) \neq \exp(-ipx)$, suggesting that one has a dynamic probability. The shift in x' for p and $-p$ should be present in such a probability and we argue that it is, namely in $i \sin(px)$. $\sin(px)$, however, cannot be the full probability, because the idea that p and $-p$ are mirror motions for the same m_0 must be present as well. This leads to the idea that the modulus of $\exp(ipx)$ represents spatial invariance, whereas the periodicity of $\cos(px)$ and $\sin(px)$ in $\exp(ipx)$ represent the spatial resolution which means that a particle may probabilistically interact with both slits of a 2-slit apparatus (separated by about \hbar/p). The fact that $\exp(ipx) \neq \exp(-ipx)$, specifically due to $\sin(px)$, means that $\exp(ipx)$ is a spatial probability in a particular frame. P and $-p$ represent different shifts in space (i.e. \hbar/p and $-\hbar/p$).